

Effects of Individualized Counselling Technique on Remediating Truancy Among Junior Secondary School Students

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of individualized counselling technique on remediating truancy among junior secondary school students. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. Forty truant students aged 11-13 were randomly selected from JS I and JS II students of Capital City Secondary School, Awka. Quasi - experimental design was used for the study. Two instruments were used. Truant identification for teachers and a checklist on children's truancy were developed and validated. Results were analysed using t -test. The experimental groups were exposed to treatment conditions, while the control group was not. The findings showed that using individual counselling techniques had significant effects on truants and consequently reduced truancy. The truants in the experimental group acquired more effective regular school behaviour. Implications of the findings were shown and recommendations were made.

Key words: truancy, secondary, individualized technique, Counselling

Introduction

Children are sent to school by their parents to study, but unfortunately some of them manifest behaviours which are not desirable (Colis, 2003). Nwosu (2006) observes that these undesirable behaviours do not enhance the maintenance and actualization of potentials of the individual. In most secondary schools in Nigeria, deviant behaviours have been manifested in various forms and at different levels ranging from relatively simple problem of lateness to school, to more serious ones as truancy (Nwosu, 2006). In Nigeria today, students stay away from school, while playing along the road or going into closets while the lessons are progressing. Odoemelum (2006) observes that some students stay in bars eating goat's head and drinking beer and palm wine, wasting their time. These behaviour problems affect both the individual and society at large. The behaviour problem retards children's and youths' socio-emotional and educational development.

Williams (2002) and Herald (2005) observe that truancy generate has physical, and health problems on children. Truancy, according to Simsons (2000) is seen as a practice of staying away from school without permission from the authority. Odoemelam (2006) also see truancy as when a child loiters, wanders, and idles about, gallivants, rigmaroles, walks about, perambulates while going to or returning from their schools. These students are not really learning, but are playing and wasting their time. The children are academically inept and fail in examinations. Anagbogu (2003) has it that truancy exposes the child to dangers like kidnapping, flogging and punishment, failure, depression, withdrawal, low self-image, stress, frustration and loss of confidence. Such children become dissatisfied with the programmed skills training. Even worse, the lives of these students are endangered as they loiter about (Ihedioha and Odoemelam, 2005). Marr and Field (2003) report that school truancy may be a common outcome of bullying.

Nwosu (2006) notes that teachers, school authorities and parents have reacted in different ways to quell students' truancy. There has been such application as scolding, denial of love, corporal punishment and suspension; expulsion meted to reduce or eliminate truancy, which appeared not to have lasting effect.

The relevance of counselling to modify students' behaviour has been considered in studies during the past two decades. Ihedioha and Odoemelam (2005) evaluate the effects of contingency contracting and modeling in the management of truancy among primary school pupils.- They concluded that these two techniques served to help in modifying their behaviour. Anagbogu (1991) advocates that teacher counsellors should utilize individual counselling techniques to help a child improve his-behaviour problems. She affirms that counselling is a learning process designed to increase adaptive behaviour and to exterminate maladaptive behaviour.

Brown and Jolie (2001) and Briggs (2003) presenting evidence from a number of studies, suggest that changes in individual participants usually occur when a high degree of genuineness, warmth, and empathic understanding were being communicated with the individual. Individual counselling, according to Wesolowez (2001) refers to a learning process in which individuals learn-about themselves, their interpersonal relationship and behaviours that advance their personal development. Thus, those with truancy problem can be made to modify their non-desirable behaviour using individualized counselling techniques. This informs the decision of this study to modify truancy behaviour among junior secondary school students using Individual Counselling Technique.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was therefore to determine the relative effects of individual counselling techniques on eliminating (modifying) truancy among students.

Hypotheses

To achieve the purpose of this study, the following hypotheses were investigated at the ,05 level of significance;

- i. There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores of the students who received individualized counselling techniques and the control group,
- ii. The mean scores of the students who received individualized counselling techniques and the control groups do not differ significantly after one month,

- iii. The mean scores of the students who received individualized counselling techniques and the control groups do not differ significantly after three months.

Methodology

This is a quasi-experimental study. The subjects for the study consisted of 201 secondary school students of Capital City Secondary School, Awka in Anambra State. The sample comprised 40 students through simple random sampling. The instrument for data collection was a researcher designed structured questionnaire. The questionnaire sheets were made up of two sections. Section A sought to ascertain the biodata of the subjects used. Section B had 15 items designed to determine the students that had the truant's behaviour tendencies.

The checklist consisted of two sections. Section A sought to ascertain the subjects biodata information, while section B had 20 items that dealt with truants' behaviour characteristics. A draft copy of the questionnaire and checklist were given to experts in Guidance and counseling and psychology for face validity. The study has treatment and the control groups. It had one 'treatment model and-a control group for pre-test, treatment and post-test and retention. The hypotheses were tested using t-test.

Results;

Table 1

t - test on the post-test mean scores of the Treatment Groups and the Control Group:..

Group	N	X	SD	df	t cal	t crit	Result
Experimental	20	63.7	10.62	38	8.21	2.02	Reject
Control	20	38.2	9.83				

Data in table 1 show that t - calculated (8.21) is greater than t - critical (2.02) at the 0.05 level of significance. .Therefore, the answer, to hypothesis one is, that there was significant difference between the post mean scores of clients who received individual counselling and the control group. The null hypothesis 1is rejected.

Table2

t - test on the post-test mean scores of the Treatment Techniques and the Control Group after one month follow-up.

N=40

Group	N	X	SD	df	teal	tcrit	Result
Experimental	20	64.6	10.85	38	8.24	2.02	Reject
Control	20	39	8.61				

In table 2 above, it was discovered that at 5 percent level of significance and 38 df, the calculated 18.24 is greater than the critical t=2.02. This indicates that HO, is rejected. Therefore, the mean

scores of clients during follow-up, after receiving individual counselling therapy and the control group differed significantly.

Table 3

t - test on the post-test mean scores of the Treatment Techniques and the Control Group after three month follow-up. N = 40

Group	N	X	SD	df	teal	tcrit	Result
Experimental	20	67.2	10.96	38	8.42	2.02	Reject
Control	20	35.6	8.54				

In table 3 above, it was discovered that at 5 percent level of significance and 38 df, the calculated 18.42 is greater than the critical 12.02. This indicates that H_0 is rejected. Therefore, the mean scores of clients during follow-up, after receiving individual counselling therapy and the control group differed significantly. The treatment group had higher mean rating than the control group.

Discussion

From this study, it was discovered that individualized counselling technique led to significant effect on remediation of truancy among junior secondary school students.

The findings stated above were in line with the suggestions of Ihedioha and Odoemelam (2005) and Anagbogu (1991), who emphasized the strength of the individual counselling technique.

Furthermore, the present findings agreed with the findings of Brown and Jolie (2001) and Briggs (2003) who suggested that changes in individual participants usually occur when the individual counselling technique is used.

In addition to the above stated findings, it was also discovered that the effect of individual counselling technique in reducing the students' truancy was still high after one month and three months of follow-up. This implies that there is high hope that all those exhibiting truancy behaviour in schools could be changed using individualized counselling technique.

Implications of the Findings

The findings of the study showed that the experimental group exposed to the individual counselling technique helped to modify their behaviour. This finding implies that use of individual counselling technique should be used in changing undesirable behaviour (truancy), Provision of counselling services to all categories of students, by qualified personnel is; implicated by this study.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Based on the findings that the individualized counselling technique, led to significant effect on the remediation of truancy among students, it is recommended that qualified; counselling psychologists should be posted to all categories of educational institutions

-Pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary institutions should help students acquire desirable behaviours.

- Furthermore, the Junior secondary schools' time-table can be so prepared to accommodate counselling.
- Teachers should help to send truant students to counsellors in their offices for proper counselling on basis of individual counselling.
- Orientation services should be organized for pupils, students, schools and the States Education Commission with the aim of making children recognize the value of education and have permanent interest in the School.

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